

UTILIZATION OF PEDAGOGICAL APPROACHES IN IMPLEMENTING THE PHILIPPINE PROFESSIONAL STANDARDS FOR TEACHERS (PPST)

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ABSTRACT

With the implementation of the Philippine Professional Standards for Teachers, the utilization of pedagogical approaches as mandated by RA 10533 is expected to reflect in achieving the teaching standards. Content knowledge and pedagogy as its domain directly related to the utilization of strategies must blend with using 2C2I1R pedagogical approaches. The link between the teaching standards and mandated pedagogy must have been established for improved practice in teaching and to achieve better learning outcomes. The study aimed to assess the extent of utilization of pedagogical approaches and awareness of proficient teachers on content knowledge and pedagogical objectives of PPST. Likewise, it identified the challenges in utilizing the constructivist, collaborative, inquiry-based, integrative, and reflective pedagogical approaches. The descriptive research design was employed in the study with a questionnaire as a data-gathering tool with focus group discussion. Respondents were 237 school heads and 366 proficient teachers from public elementary schools. In the utilization of pedagogical approaches, the constructivist assessment, organization of collaborative reflective groups, real-life inquiry activities, and integrative application were highly utilized but with deposition in using triangulation assessment and action research application. Content knowledge and pedagogical objectives dealing with the application of learners' background, vocabulary development, and creating classroom conditions for interaction were well-known by teachers with second thoughts on using contradictory points and creative thinking tools, and off-classroom activity. When grouped according to profile variables, there is a significant relationship between the highest educational attainment and the utilization of pedagogical approaches as well as awareness of content knowledge and pedagogy. Transmitting critical and creative thinking and systematic investigation and revitalizing reflection were the challenges in implementing 2C2I1R pedagogical approaches. Based on the results of the study, the researcher proposed a teacher's management guide considering the inquiry-based and reflective approaches and guidelines in attaining the PPST pedagogical objectives.

Keywords: educational management, pedagogical approaches, descriptive survey, Philippines